

EFFECTIVENESS OF EACH ONE TEACH ONE ON READING SKILLS OF GRADE 3 LEARNERS

Glicel K. Salvador¹, Amelia V. Tulagan², Belinda M. Samera³,
Nenette M. Lacuarin⁴, Victoria E. Tamban, Ed.D.⁵

¹Malaban Elementary School , Department of Education, Philippines

²Malaban Elementary School , Department of Education, Philippines

³Malaban Elementary School ,³Department of Education, Philippines

⁴Malaban Elementary School , Department of Education, Philippines

⁵College of Teacher Education ,Laguna State Polytechnic University, Philippines

ABSTRACT : *This study aimed in determining the effectiveness of “Each One Teach One” approach among Grade 3 reading skills. Descriptive evaluative research design was employed in this study. The respondents of the study were the 36 learners from Grade III level of Malaban Elementary School, School Year 2018-2019. Quasi experimental research design was applied in this study. Mean, Standard Deviation, and t-test were used for statistical analysis. It was revealed that the learners in the pretest approach and conventional approach were beginning level in terms of rhyme, oral blending and oral segmentation. It was revealed that the learners in the pretend play group performed better in their phonemic awareness in terms of rhyme oral blending, and oral segmentation compared to the conventional group in their formative tests and posttest. These results means that the pretend play group performed better than the conventional group. This result described that the pretend play is effective in enhancing the phonemic awareness of the kindergarten learners in terms of rhyme, oral blending, and oral segmentation. Based on the findings here are the conclusions of this study. The null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference between the formative tests and posttest of the two group of kindergarten learners on their phonemic awareness and reading readiness is rejected same with the hypothesis that there is no significant difference on the pre-test and post-test mean scores of the learners on their phonemic awareness assessment using the conventional approach as well as that there is no significant difference on the pre-test and post-test mean scores of the learners on their phonemic awareness assessment using the pretend play approach. Based on the findings and conclusion the following were the suggestion or recommendations of the researcher; the pretend play approach may continue to use in teaching not only in phonemic awareness but also in other topics in kindergarten for the evidence showed that this approach is much effective than the conventional approach in phonemic awareness of the learners, other approaches similar to pretend play may be also used for this study focus only using the pretend play in phonemic awareness.*

KEYWORDS - *each one teach one, effectiveness, reading skills, grade three learners*

I. INTRODUCTION

Learning is a practice of reading, learning, and developing new skills for students (Olivar, 2014).

The Department of Education (DepEd) initiated "Every Child A Reader Program" (ECARP), through DepEd Memorandum No.402.2004 and Administrative Order No. 324, recognizing the importance of learning and in line with the introduction of the K to 12 Basic Education Programme. It aims at educating elementary students with expected education in reading and writing to make them young readers and writers free.

Often recognized as the Republic Act No. 10533 is the 2013 Enhanced Basic Education Act. It has enhanced the Philippine Basic Education System by strengthening its curriculum and increasing the number of years for basic education. According to Section 10.2.a "The program must be learner-centered, rigorous and appropriate for development. In this way, the department actively promotes strategies and ways to enhance the

teaching-learning process. Teachers are given seminars, training sessions and workshops to improve their ability to become effective facilitators.

Schools in the Philippines have introduced numerous reading programs that improve the success of oral reading through decoding, fluidity and word recognition. However, most empirical evidence supporting these modes of reading interventions is not evident in local literature (Reinking & Watkins, 2003). Some of the reading programs in the Philippines involving. Adult supervision is important for a child to learn how to read. In the U.S., the No Child Left Behind (NCLB) Act targets children's literacy rate that focuses on two main topics that the government believes the children need progress on: Reading and Mathematics. This work focused on evaluating an adult supervision reading intervention. Adult guidance is called scaffolding in terms of helping a child learn (Palmer, Zhang, Taylor, & Leclere, 2010).

To create an active model to educate students with reading skills from the public school, testing is done to find out the status of their reading skills.

Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) is one of the assessment methods used. It measures students' reading skills through word recognition and pupil reading understanding in English and Filipino, specifically by getting the percentage of word recognition accuracy and the percentage of correct answers to understanding questions based on the set of reading level criteria.

The students are grouped into four levels based on the scale of the Phil-IRI: non-reader, annoyance, academic and autonomous. Pupil under the reading level of frustration continues to refrain from reading by rejecting it. The pupil can read only when instructed in the instructional reading level, while the pupil can read alone with ease without the teacher's guidance.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory of Development became a major influence in the field of psychology and education (Milner, H. R., and Woolfolk Hoy, A., 2003). This theory stated that students learn through social interactions and their culture – much different from Piaget's theory that stated children act on their environment to learn. Through what Vygotsky called "dialogues," we socially interact and communicate with others to learn the cultural values of our society. Vygotsky also believed that "human activities take place in cultural settings and cannot be understood apart from these settings" (Woolfolk, A., 45). Therefore, our culture helps shape our cognition.

It was shown in Figure 1, the conceptual framework of this study wherein the independent variable is the utilization of innovative and creative supplementary reading materials.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Descriptive research design and experimental design were used in the study. Descriptive research design is a purposeful method for collecting, evaluating, classifying and tabulating information on prevailing conditions, behaviors, patterns and relationships between causes and effects, and for proper and reliable analysis of such data with or without the aid of statistical intervention (Shuttleworth, 2008).

The participants of the study were the 44 learners in frustration level of Grade 3 consist of 22 experimental group and 22 comparison group of Malaban Elementary School.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It was shown in table 1 that the level of reading performance of Grade 3 learners on their pretest were both frustration

Table 1. PHIL-IRI Pretest Mean Score Reading Performance of Experimental and Comparison Group

Group	Pre-test (MPS)	SD	Level
Experimental	46.68%	4.43	Frustration
Comparison	46.68%	4.43	Frustration

Legend: 80-100% (Independent); 59-79% (Average) and 58% & below (Below Average)

It was shown that the level of reading performance of Grade 3 learners on their pretest were both frustration with an MPS of 46.68%, SD of 4.43 and frustration level.

This supported the needs to a teaching approach and strategy to enhance the learners reading performance.

It was shown in table 2, the posttest mean performance of the learners on their pretest and posttest in reading.

Table 2. PHIL-IRI Posttest Mean Percentage Score Reading Performance of Experimental and Comparison Group

Group	Posttest (MPS)	SD	Level
Experimental	85.18%	3.42	Independent
Comparison	52.23%	6.45	Frustration

Legend: 80-100% (Independent); 59-79% (Instruction) and 58% & below (Frustration)

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between Pretest and Posttest Mean Percentage Score of the Grade 3 Learners in Experimental Group

Group	Overall Mean	Mean Difference	t-value
Experimental	85.18%	32.65	**23.214
Comparison	52.23%		

**p-value ≤ 0.01 ; *p-value ≤ 0.05

The results revealed that the PHIL-IRI posttest mean percentage score reading performance of experimental and comparison found highly significantly different with t-value 23.314 and 32.65 mean difference which determined that the teaching approaches is effective.

Table 4 shows the pretest and posttest mean percentage score of experimental group.

Table 4. Test on the Significant Difference between Pre and Post Tests Mean Percentage Score of the Grade 3 Learners in Experimental Group

Test Type	Overall Mean	Mean Difference	t-value
Posttest	85.18%		

Pretest	46.68%	38.50	**28.326
---------	--------	-------	----------

***p*-value ≤ 0.01 ; * *p*-value ≤ 0.05

There is highly significant difference between the PHIL-IRI posttest mean percentage score reading performance of experimental and comparison group with *t*-value of 28.326 with mean difference of 38.50 which determined that the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 5 reveals the test of significant difference between pretest and posttest of comparison group.

Table 5. Test on the Significant Difference between Pre and Post Tests Mean Percentage Score of the Grade 3 Learners in Comparison Group

Test Type	Overall Mean	Mean Difference	<i>t</i> -value
Posttest	52.23%	5.55	**4.84
Pretest	46.68%		

***p*-value ≤ 0.01 ; * *p*-value ≤ 0.05

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The researchers concluded that the findings showed significant difference on the reading performance of the respondents. The null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference between the formative tests and posttest of the two group of kindergarten learners on their phonemic awareness and reading readiness is rejected same with the hypothesis that there is no significant difference on the pre-test and post-test mean scores of the learners on their phonemic awareness assessment using the conventional approach as well as that there is no significant difference on the pre-test and post-test mean scores of the learners on their phonemic awareness assessment using the pretend play approach.

The following were the suggestion or recommendations of the researcher; the pretend play approach may continue to use in teaching not only in phonemic awareness but also in other topics in kindergarten for the evidence showed that this approach is much effective than the conventional approach in phonemic awareness of the learners, other approaches similar to pretend play may be also used for this study focus only using the pretend play in phonemic awareness, and further study for a broader scope may be conducted for it only limits 68 kindergarten learners.

V. Acknowledgements

The authors would like to humbly thank the Hon. Mayor Arman R. Dimaguila of Biñan City, Mr. RonualdoRoscaín, the Planning Officer of Biñan City, the President of Laguna State Polytechnic University, Dr. Mario R. Briones, the Vice President of R & D, Dr. Roberto C. Agatep, the Director of R &D, Prof. Christian Paul de la Cruz, Associate Dean Karen A. Manaig of College of Teacher Education , and the student-participants for their support on the completion of this study.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Every Child A Reader Program" (ECARP), through DepEd Memorandum No.402.2004 and Administrative Order No. 324, recognizing the importance of learning and in line with the introduction of the K to 12 Basic Education Programme
- [2] <http://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/downloads/2013/05may/20130515-RA-10533-BSA.pdf>
- [3] Milner, H. R., and Woolfolk Hoy, A. (2003). Teacher self-efficacy and retaining talented teachers: A case study of an African American teacher. *Teach. Teach. Educ.* 19: 263-276.
- [4] Olivar, L. L., Manalo, J. A Palma, A. M., Ramirez, V. H., Gemino, K. L., Caiga, B. T. (2014). Awareness of Maritime Students in Lyceum International Maritime Academy on the Drop Everything and Read (DEAR) Program , *Academic Research International*, 5(3), 206-213.

- [5] Palmer, Zhang, Taylor, & Leclere, (2010), Language proficiency, reading, and the Chinese-speaking english language learner facilitating the L1-L2 Connection
- [6] Reinking, D., Eakle, A. J., Hubbard, B., Hung, H. T., Lim, H. W., & Park, M. (2003, November). New technologies of reading and writing: A database modeling a dynamic, collaborative scholarly resource.
- [7] Shuttlesworth, M. (2008) Case Study Research Design. <https://explorable.com/case-study-research-design>